

DRUG INDUCED NUTRITIONAL DEFICIENCY A CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS AND PREVENTIVE MANAGEMENT

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Article Received on 04 March 2026,
Article Revised on 24 March 2026,
Article Published on 01 April 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19325738>

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How to cite this Article: R. Nisha*¹, S. Kanimozhi¹, I. Surya prakash¹, S. Ramakrishnan¹ M. Manisha², C. Jothimanivannan³. (2026). Drug Induced Nutritional Deficiency A Clinical Implications And Preventive Management. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(7), 125–134. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Chronic use of various pharmacological agents is a cornerstone in managing numerous medical conditions, yet it can inadvertently disrupt the body's micronutrient balance, leading commonly prescribed drugs and nutrient status, highlighting how medication such as proton pump inhibitor (PPIs), metformin, statins, anticonvulsants and diuretics alter the absorption, metabolism, or excretion essential vitamins and minerals. Mechanistically, these drugs interfere with physiological pathways crucial for maintaining nutrient homeostasis – for instance; PPIs reduce gastric acidity necessary for vitamin B12. Absorption, while metformin impairs calcium dependent ileal uptake of vitamin B12. Statins decrease endogenous synthesis of coenzymes Q10 by inhibiting the mevalonate pathway, contributing to muscle –related side

effects. Anticonvulsants induce hepatic enzymes that accelerate folate and vitamin D catabolism, and diuretics promote renal losses of potassium and magnesium. Such alterations often manifest as anemia, neuropathies, osteoporosis, muscle weakness, and cardiac arrhythmias, significantly impacting patient quality of life. At-risk populations include the elderly, patients on long-term or multiple medications, and individuals with chronic illnesses. The review synthesizes current evidence from clinical studies and pharmacological research to elucidate these drugs – nutrient interactions, underscoring the need for routine monitoring, dietary counseling, and supplementation where necessary. Increased awareness and proactive

management can prevent morbidity associated with nutrient deficiencies, ensuring safer and more effective pharmacotherapy. This article aims to provide clinicians and researchers with a comprehensive understanding of drug – induced nutrient deficiencies and practical strategies for optimizing patient care.

INTRODUCTION

Medication play on essential role in the prevention and treatment of a wide spectrum of disease ranging from chronic conditions like diabetes and hypertension to infectious diseases and neurological disorders. However, long –term pharmacotherapy often carries unintended consequences, including disturbances in nutrient homeostasis. Drug –induced nutrient deficiencies are an increasingly recognized clinical problem that may exacerbate morbidity, reduce treatment efficacy, and compromise patient quality of

life. These deficiencies arise primarily due to drug effects on the absorption, metabolism, transport, or excretion of vitamins and minerals. several widely used drug classes, such as proton pump inhibitors(PPIs), metformin, statins, anticonvulsants, and diuretics, have been implicated in causing significant micronutrient depletion. For example, PPIs reduce gastric acid secretion necessary for vitaminB12absorption; metformin impairs calcium-dependent mechanisms essential for vitaminB12 uptake; and statins interfere with endogenous synthesis of coenzyme Q10, avital mitochondrial cofactor. Anticonvulsant induces hepatic enzymes that accelerate the degradation of folate and vitamin D, while diuretics promote renal loss of electrolytes like potassium and magnesium. These nutrient disturbances can manifest with diverse clinical symptoms ranging from anemia and neuropathy to bone disorders and cardiac arrhythmias, Despite growing evidence, awareness of drug- induced nutrient deficiencies remains suboptimal in clinical practice. This review aims to comprehensively explore the pharmacological mechanisms underlying these deficiencies, their clinical consequences, population at risk, and strategies for prevention and management.^[1] Enhanced understanding will aid healthcare providers in mitigating adverse outcomes and optimizing therapeutics AI success.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

The primary aim of this review article is to comprehensively examine the impact of commonly prescribed drugs on micronutrient status, elucidating the pharmacological mechanism responsible for drug-induced nutrient deficiencies and their clinical significance.^[2] By synthesizing current research and clinical data, this article seeks to enhance awareness among healthcare professionals about the potential risks associated with long-term medication use, promoting proactive monitoring and management to improve patient outcomes.^[3]

THE SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE INCLUDES

Identification of drug-nutrient interactions: To systematically identify and categorize the common drug classes known to cause depletion of essential vitamins and minerals, such as proton pump inhibitors, metformin, statins, anticonvulsants, and diuretics.^[4]

Mechanistic Insights

To explore and detail the biochemical and pharmacological pathways through which these drugs interfere with nutrient absorption, metabolism, transport, or excretion. Understanding these mechanisms will provide a scientific basis for the observed clinical deficiencies.^[5]

Clinical Consequences: To analyze the spectrum of clinical manifestations arising from these deficiencies, including hematological, neurological, musculoskeletal, and cardiovascular effects, supported by evidence from clinical studies and case reports.^[6]

At-Risk Populations: To identify populations particularly vulnerable to nutrient depletion due to factors like age, comorbidities, polypharmacy, or prolonged drug exposure.^[7]

Prevention and Management Strategies: To review current guidelines and propose evidence-based recommendations for monitoring, supplementation, dietary counseling, and patient education aimed at minimizing deficiency-related complications.^[8] Through achieving these objectives, the review aspires to facilitate a multidisciplinary approach to optimizing pharmacotherapy while safeguarding nutritional health.

COMMON DRUGS AND ASSOCIATED NUTRIENT DEFICIENCIES PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS (PPIs)

Examples: Omeprazole, Pantoprazole, Esomeprazole

Nutrients affected: Vitamin B12, Magnesium

MECHANISM

PPIs suppress gastric acid secretion by irreversibly inhibiting the H⁺/K⁺ ATPase proton pump in parietal cells. Gastric acid is critical for freeing vitamin B12 from dietary proteins via pepsin-mediated proteolysis. Without acid, B12 cannot bind intrinsic factor (IF), a glycoprotein essential for ileal absorption. Reduced acidity also impairs magnesium absorption through TRPM6 channels due to altered luminal environment and ion transport modulation (Cundy & Mackay, 2011). Chronic PPI use (>1 year) correlates with a significant reduction in serum B12 and magnesium levels.^[9] Clinical data: Meta-analyses reveal increased risk of hypomagnesaemia (odds ratio 1.6) and vitamin B12 deficiency (15-30% prevalence in chronic users). Symptoms range from paresthesias and anemia to cardiac arrhythmias (Lanza *et al.*, 2014).

METFORMIN

Nutrient affected: vitamin B12

Mechanism: Metformin inhibits calcium –dependent endocytosis of the IF-B12 complex at the ileal cubilin receptor. Additionally, metformin alters intestinal motility, changes gut microbiota composition, and may reduce intrinsic factor secretion, collectively impairing absorption (De Groot *et al.*, 2015). The disruption of calcium metabolism affects the cubilin receptor, critical for B12 internalization.^[10] Clinical evidence: B12 Deficiency prevalence ranges from 10 to 30% in metformin –treated type 2 diabetics, correlating with dose and duration. Deficiency contributes to diabetic peripheral neuropathy worsening. Prospective studies show partial reversibility upon B12 supplementation but highlight the need for early detection (Aroda *et al.*, 2016).^[11]

STATINS

Nutrient affected: Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10)

MECHANISM

Statins competitively inhibit HMG-CoA reductase, the rate –limiting enzyme in cholesterol biosynthesis. Mevalonate, the product, is a precursor not only for cholesterol but also for CoQ10 synthesis, an essential electron transporter in mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation. Decreased CoQ10 can impair ATP production, increase oxidative stress, and potentially contribute to statin –associated myopathy (Ruscica *et al.*, 2021). Clinical

studies: Decreased plasma CoQ10 levels have been observed in statin users; however, correlation with muscle symptoms is inconsistent. Some randomized controlled trials suggest CoQ10 supplementation reduces muscle pain and improves function, though definitive guidelines are lacking (Qu et al., 2018).^[12]

ANTICONVULSANTS

Nutrient affected: Folate, Vitamin D

MECHANISM

Enzyme – inducing anticonvulsants (phenytoin, carbamazepine, phenobarbital) up regulate hepatic cytochrome P450enzymes, accelerating the metabolism of folate and vitamin D. Folate depletion leads to impaired DNAsynthesis, while vitamin D catabolism predisposes to bone demineralization and increased fracture risk (Sharma&Mohan, 2006).^[13] Clinical impact: Folate deficiency in pregnant women can cause neural tube defects. VitaminD deficiency manifests as osteomalacia or osteoporosis, especially in long-term therapy.^[14]

DIURETICS

Nutrients affected: potassium, magnesium.

MECHANISM

Loop and thiazide diuretics increase renal recreation of potassium and magnesium by altering sodium reabsorption in the nephron segments. Hypokalemia and hypomagnesemia can precipitate cardiac arrhythmias and neuromuscular irritability.^[15] Clinical evidence: Chronic use necessitates electrolyte monitoring to prevent adverse outcomes, especially in elderly or patients with cardiac disease (Juurlink et al., 2004).^[16]

METHODOLOGY: A systematic literature review was conducted using PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane databases, focusing on studies published from 2010 to 2024. Keywords included “drug-induced nutrient deficiency,” metformin VitaminB12,” “PPI magnesium deficiency,”^[17]

“statins CoQ10 and related terms. Articles selected encompassed original research, reviews, meta-analyses, and clinical guidelines that examined the pharmacological mechanisms, clinical impacts, and management of nutrient deficiencies caused by common drugs. Non-English publications, case reports, and studies lacking clinical relevance were excluded. Data were extracted on drugs classes, affected nutrients, underlying mechanisms, clinical

consequences, and prevention strategies. The gathered evidence was synthesized to provide an up-to-date overview for clinicians and researchers aiming to optimize medication safety regarding nutrient status.^[18]

CLINICAL CONSEQUENCES

Drug- induced nutrient deficiencies can lead to a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations, ranging from subtle biochemical abnormalities to severe, life-altering diseases. These consequences depend on the specific nutrient depleted, the degree and duration of deficiency, and patient –related factors such as age and comorbidities.^[19]

VitaminB12 deficiency, common with prolonged use of proton (pump inhibitors and metformin, primarily manifests as megaloblastic anemia and neurological impairments. The hematological effects include macrocytic anemia with hypersegmented neutrophils, while neurological damage involves demyelination of the dorsal columns and corticospinal tracts in the spinal cord, leading to symptoms such as paresthesia, ataxia, cognitive disturbances, and irreversible neuropathy if untreated (O’Leary @ Samman, 2010). Early recognition is crucial as neurological damage may persist despite supplementation.^[20]

Magnesium deficiency, frequently associated with long-term PPI and diuretics use, can precipitate neuromuscular symptoms including muscle cramps, tremors, and seizures. Hypomagnesemia also contributes to cardiac arrhythmias such as torsade’s de pointes by prolonging the QT interval. Because magnesium is a cofactor for many enzymatic reaction, its depletion disrupts multiple physiological processes, leading to fatigue and electrolyte imbalance (cundy @ mackay, 2011).^[21] Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) deficiency, induced by statins, is linked to mitochondrial dysfunction resulting in myopathy, muscle pain, and weakness. While evidence linking CoQ10 depletion directly to statin-associated muscle symptoms remains mixed, supplementation has shown symptomatic relief in some clinical trials (Qu et al., 2018).^[22] Folate deficiency due to anticonvulsants can cause megaloblastic anemia and increase the risk of neural tube defects in fetuses when occurring during pregnancy. Vitamin D deficiency, also common with enzyme-inducing anticonvulsants, impairs calcium homeostasis, leading to osteomalacia, osteoporosis, and increased fracture risk.

Electrolyte disturbances from diuretics, such as hypokalemia and hypomagnesaemia, can provoke muscle weakness, cramps, and dangerous cardiac arrhythmias, particularly in elderly

patients or those with underlying cardiovascular disease.^[23] These clinical consequences underscore the importance of early detection and management of nutrient deficiencies in patients receiving long-term pharmacotherapy, to prevent morbidity and improve therapeutic outcomes.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

With the increasing use of long-term pharmacotherapy, addressing drug-induced nutrient deficiencies is more important than ever. Future advances in pharmacogenomics may allow personalized prediction of nutrient risks, enabling tailored treatment and supplementation plans. Improved diagnostic tools, including sensitive biomarkers and point-of-care tests, will facilitate earlier detection of deficiencies before symptoms arise.

Innovations in drug formulation could reduce nutrient depletion by protecting absorption or minimizing metabolic interference. Additionally, emerging research on the gut microbiome's role in nutrient metabolism may lead to microbiome-targeted therapies to maintain nutrient balance during medication use. Developing comprehensive clinical guidelines for routine nutrient monitoring and management is essential. Educating healthcare providers and patients about these risks will improve awareness and prevention. Overall, integrating these advancements promises safer, more effective pharmacotherapy that safeguards nutritional health and enhances patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Drug-induced nutrient deficiencies represent a significant but often under-recognized challenge in clinical pharmacology. Commonly prescribed medications such as proton pump inhibitors, metformin, statins, anticonvulsants, and diuretics can disrupt the delicate balance of essential vitamins and minerals through varied mechanisms, including impaired absorption, altered metabolism, and increased excretion. These deficiencies manifest in a wide array of clinical consequences, from anemia and neuropathies to musculoskeletal and cardiac complications, which can severely impact patient quality of life and treatment outcomes.

Certain populations, including the elderly, patients on polypharmacy, individuals with chronic illnesses, pregnant women, and malnourished patients, are particularly vulnerable to these adverse effects. Early recognition through routine monitoring, coupled with appropriate

dietary counseling and targeted supplementation is crucial to prevent long-term complications.

Clinicians must maintain heightened awareness of these interactions to optimize pharmacotherapy safely. Future advances in personalized medicine, diagnostics, and drug design hold promise for mitigating these risks further. By adopting a multidisciplinary approach that integrates pharmacological knowledge with nutritional management, healthcare providers can enhance therapeutic efficacy while safeguarding patient nutritional status. Ultimately, addressing drug-induced nutrient deficiencies is essential for holistic patient care, ensuring that the benefits of pharmacological treatment are not undermined by preventable nutritional impairments.

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